

NITRATO-LEAD^{II} COMPLEX AND HYDROLYSIS OF LEAD^{II} IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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The same type of solubility as observed in the previous communication (this *issue*, p. 387) has also been observed in nitric acid and in sodium nitrate solutions. The solubilities in sodium nitrate and nitric acid are respectively greater than those in sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid of the same ionic strength. The latter observation is probably due to the formation of nitrate-lead complex. In neutral solution (in saturated solution of lead iodate in sodium nitrate) the complex mostly consists of hydroxo-nitrate-lead complex, $PbOH \cdot NO_3$, whereas in acid solution this complex together with nitrate-lead complex, $PbNO_3^+$, exist. The equilibrium constants of the reactions:

have been determined and are 0.161, 3.83, 4.94 and 0.186 respectively.

The existence of nitrate-lead complex $PbNO_3^+$ has been reported by several workers (Righellato and Davies, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1930, **26**, 592; Plake, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1932, **A162**, 257) Zikler, *ibid.*, 1932, **A163**, 1; Nasanen, *Ann. Acad. Sci. Fennicase, All Chem.*, 1945, No. 13, 1; Hershenson, Smith and Hume, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 508). The equilibrium constant of the reaction

has been found to lie between 1.6 and 15. This difference in the equilibrium constant might be accounted for as due to different experimental conditions. This, however, does not lead to the actual factor responsible for this variation. Further investigation was thought to be necessary. The authors in the previous paper (this *issue*, p. 387) have discussed the effect of the variation of the concentration of hydrogen ion on the solubility of lead iodate. It has been shown that in a saturated solution of lead iodate in perchloric acid solution, the product of the concentration of lead ion and the square of the concentration of iodate ion is not constant at all p_H , but directly proportional to the concentration of H^+ .

$$\frac{[Pb^{2+}] \times [IO_3^-]^2}{[H^+]} = K_1 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)^*$$

They have further shown that

$$4S^3 = K_2 \times [H^+] + K_1 \times k_1 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)^\dagger$$

where k_1 is the first hydrolysis constant, that is the equilibrium constant of the reaction,

$$\frac{[PbOH^+] \times [H^+]}{[Pb^{2+}]} = k_1 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

* Eq. (8) in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*)

† Eq. (9-3) in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*)

In the neutral solution (saturated solution of lead iodate in sodium perchlorate solution) the concentration of hydrogen ion being small, the factor $K_s \times [H^+]$ in equation (3) is small, and hence,

$$4S_0^3 = K_s \times k_1, \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

where S_0 is the solubility of lead iodate in sodium perchlorate solution. Substituting the value of K_s and k_1 from equations (2) and (5) respectively, the equation (6) can be written as

$$4S_0^3 = [PbOH^+] \times [IO_3^-]^2 = K_s \times k_1, \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

The product of the concentration of $PbOH^+$ ion and the square of the concentration of iodate ion is constant.

These results indicate appreciable hydrolysis of lead ion in aqueous solution, and hence, the concentration of lead ion cannot be taken as equal to total lead in the solution at all p_n from zero to seven. The variation in the value of the formation constant of nitrate-lead complex, observed by various workers, might be due to hydrolysis of lead ion in aqueous solution. To verify this, the solubilities of lead iodate in (i) sodium perchlorate, (ii) perchloric acid, (iii) mixtures of sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid, (iv) sodium nitrate, (v) nitric acid and (vi) mixtures of sodium nitrate and nitric acid were determined at 35° by the method described in the previous paper of the authors (*loc. cit.*) and the results are shown in Tables IA, IB, IC, IIA, IIB and IIC respectively.

TABLE IA

[NaClO ₄].	$S \times 10^5$.
0.30	9.860
0.25	9.520
0.20	9.175
0.18	9.005
0.16	8.660
0.14	8.485
0.12	8.230
0.10	8.060
0.08	7.720
0.06	7.205
0.04	6.860
0.02	6.515

TABLE IIA

[NaNO ₃].	$S \times 10^5$.	[PbOH ⁺] $\times 10^5$.	[Complex] $\times 10^5$.	K_1 .
0.30	13.35	5.379	7.971	4.94
0.25	12.08	5.913	7.163	4.85
0.20	11.55	5.792	5.758	4.97
0.18	11.21	5.808	5.402	5.17
0.16	10.69	5.682	5.008	5.51
0.14	10.27	5.798	4.427	5.00
0.12	9.840	5.757	4.083	5.51
0.10	9.810	5.439	4.371	8.06
0.08	8.810	5.927	2.883	6.08
0.06	8.210	5.562	2.648	7.93
0.04	7.530	5.693	1.837	8.07
0.02	6.840	5.913	0.927	7.84

TABLE IB

[HClO ₄]. S × 10 ⁶ .
0.30
0.25
0.20
0.18
0.16
0.14
0.12
0.10
0.08
0.05
0.04
0.02

TABLE IIB

[HNO ₃]. S × 10 ³ .	[PbOH ⁺] × 10 ⁴ .	[Pb ²⁺] × 10 ⁵ .	[Complex] × 10 ⁶ .	k ₁ .	K ₁ .	K.	
0.30	20.21	2.520	6.685	10.13	0.113	13.6	5.05
0.25	17.88	2.698	5.793	9.389	0.116	13.9	6.48
0.20	15.79	3.099	5.171	7.540	0.120	12.1	7.27
0.18	14.72	3.368	5.023	6.329	0.121	10.5	7.00
0.16	13.86	3.380	4.545	5.935	0.120	11.0	8.16
0.14	13.00	3.616	4.225	5.159	0.127	10.2	8.72
0.12	11.98	3.886	3.943	4.151	0.118	8.90	8.77
0.10	10.96	4.358	2.982	3.620	0.143	8.31	12.10
0.08	10.180	4.440	2.548	3.192	0.139	8.99	15.70
0.05	9.565	4.087	2.312	3.166	0.106	12.90	22.80
0.04	8.040	4.980	2.096	1.946	0.096	9.86	23.20
0.02	6.845	5.995	0.940			7.96	

DISCUSSION

The solubility of lead iodate in nitric acid is greater than that in sodium nitrate of the same concentration, as observed in the perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate system. The solubilities in nitric acid and sodium nitrate, however, are respectively greater than that in perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate solutions of the same concentration. If the variations in the solubility in sodium perchlorate solutions of different concentrations are assumed to be due to the variation in the ionic strength, the increase in the solubility in sodium nitrate solution of the same ionic strength is most probably due to the formation of nitrato-lead complex. The same argument is applicable to the solutions in nitric acid.

Reactions in Neutral Medium

S₀, S, S₁ and S₂ are respectively the solubilities of lead iodate in sodium perchlorate, perchloric acid (or mixture of sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid), sodium nitrate and nitric acid (or mixture of sodium nitrate and nitric acid) solutions of the same ionic strength.

It has been shown in the previous paper (*loc. cit.*) that in a saturated solution of lead iodate in sodium perchlorate solution, the concentration of lead ion is very small compared to the concentration of PbOH⁺, and can be neglected. The concentration of PbOH⁺ is given by equation (7) and can be determined by substituting the values of S₀ and [IO₃⁻]. In sodium nitrate solution, besides PbOH⁺, the nitrato complex exists but the ionic strength being the same, the equation (7) holds good. The concentration of iodate ion is 2S₁. Hence,

$$[PbOH^+] = \frac{S_0^a}{S_1^3} \dots \dots (8)$$

TABLE IC

Mixture		Mixture				Mixture				Mixture			
[HClO ₄], [NaClO ₄], S × 10 ⁵ .	[HNO ₃], [NaNO ₃], S × 10 ⁵ .	[PbOH ⁺] × 10 ⁵ .	[Pb ²⁺] × 10 ⁵ .	[Complex] × 10 ⁵ .	K ₁ .								
0.30	0.00	15.17	0.30	0.00	20.41	2.520	6.685	10.33	0.114	13.7	5.05		
0.25	0.05	14.23	0.25	0.05	18.99	2.655	5.434	10.89	0.122	13.8	6.68		
0.20	0.10	13.43	0.20	0.10	17.79	3.029	4.603	10.16	0.132	11.2	7.36		
0.18	0.12	12.90	0.18	0.12	17.11	3.274	4.057	10.78	0.147	11.0	8.76		
0.16	0.14	12.64	0.16	0.14	16.60	3.439	3.861	9.160	0.144	8.87	7.99		
0.14	0.16	12.21	0.14	0.16	15.92	3.782	3.397	8.741	0.152	7.70	8.58		
0.12	0.18	11.86	0.12	0.18	15.48	4.026	2.979	8.425	0.161	6.98	9.43		
0.10	0.20	11.51	0.10	0.20	14.80	4.376	2.584	7.840	0.169	5.97	10.10		
0.08	0.22	11.16	0.08	0.22	14.38	4.635	2.084	7.661	0.178	5.51	12.30		
0.06	0.24	10.72	0.06	0.24	13.69	5.041	1.436	7.313	0.210	4.84	17.00		
0.04	0.26	10.37	0.04	0.26	13.44	5.196	0.847	7.447	0.246	4.79	29.30		
0.02	0.28	9.86	0.02	0.28	13.35	5.378							

TABLE IIIA

*μ.	[PbOH.NO ₂] × 10 ⁵ .	[PbNO ₂ ⁺] × 10 ⁵ .	K.	K ₂ .	*μ.	[PbOH.NO ₂] × 10 ⁵ .	[PbNO ₂ ⁺] × 10 ⁵ .	K.	K ₁ .
0.30	3.735	6.575	3.28	0.170	0.30	3.735	6.575	3.28	0.170
0.25	3.271	6.118	4.13	0.134	0.30	3.821	7.069	4.34	0.135
0.20	3.080	4.440	4.29	0.139	0.30	4.342	5.818	4.20	0.149
0.18	3.137	3.192	3.53	0.177	0.30	4.692	6.088	5.00	0.139
0.16	2.980	2.955	4.06	0.161	0.30	4.929	4.331	3.74	0.229
0.14	2.888	2.271	3.84	0.176	0.30	5.421	3.320	3.26	0.229
0.12	2.756	1.395	2.95	0.217	0.30	5.771	2.655	2.97	0.261
0.10	2.651	0.969	3.25	0.274					
0.08	2.160	1.032	5.06	0.267					

μ = Ionic strength.

The concentration of PbOH^+ is determined by equation (8) for the sodium nitrate system. The concentration of the complex is given by

$$[\text{Complex}] = S_1 - [\text{PbOH}^+] \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

The simplest reaction for the formation of the complex might be

without involving any change in the concentration of hydrogen ion. The equilibrium constant K_1 is given by

$$\frac{[\text{PbOH} \cdot \text{NO}_3^-]}{[\text{PbOH}^+] \times [\text{NO}_3^-]} = K_1 \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

Assuming the whole of the complex to be present as $\text{PbOH} \cdot \text{NO}_3$, the equilibrium constant is calculated. The concentration of nitrate ion is taken as equal to the concentration of the sodium nitrate since the concentration of the complex is very small compared to the concentration of sodium nitrate. The calculated values of K_1 are shown in Table IIA. The values are fairly constant. Though irregular, there is a tendency of the constant to increase with decreasing ionic strength of the solution. The value of K_1 , however, does not strictly indicate the complex to be $\text{PbOH} \cdot \text{NO}_3$, though it is probable. If the reaction be

the equilibrium constant would be very nearly constant since the difference in p_H of the various solutions would not be measurable, and the p_H would be very nearly constant. This would, however, be indicated from the solubilities in nitric acid.

Reactions in Acid Medium

In nitric acid Pb^{2+} , PbOH^+ and the complex (or complexes) would be in equilibrium with solid lead iodate. The concentration of iodate ion is $2S_2$. Hence,

$$[\text{PbOH}^+] = \frac{S_0^3}{S_2^2} \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

In perchloric acid (of the same concentration as nitric acid), the solubility is S . According to equation (3), $4S^3$ is equal to $(K_s \times [\text{H}^+] + K_s k_1)$. $K_s \times k_1$ is equal to $4S_0^3$. Hence,

$$4S^3 = 4S_0^3 + K_s \times [\text{H}^+] \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

Substituting the value of K_s from equation (2), the equation (13) reduces to

$$4S^3 - 4S_0^3 = [\text{Pb}^{2+}] \times [\text{IO}_3^-]^2 \quad \dots \quad (14)$$

S and S_0 are the solubilities in sodium perchlorate and perchloric acid, and the former is constant if ionic strength is constant, and the latter is constant if p_H and ionic strength are constant. Hence, the product of the concentration of lead ion and square of the concentration of iodate ion is constant at a given p_H and ionic strength and is equal to $(4S^3 - 4S_0^3)$. In nitric acid (or mixture of nitric acid and sodium nitrate) of the same p_H and the same ionic strength as perchloric acid (or mixture of perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate), the equation (14) would hold good. The concentration of lead ion is given by

$$[\text{Pb}^{2+}] = \frac{S^3 - S_0^3}{S_2^2} \quad \dots \quad (15)$$

The concentration of the complex (or complexes) is

$$[\text{Complex}] = S_2 - [\text{Pb}^{2+}] - [\text{PbOH}^+] \quad \dots \quad (16)$$

The complex might be $\text{PbOH}\cdot\text{NO}_3$ or PbNO_3^+ or both. The formation of the latter may be represented by equation (17) and equilibrium constant K by (18).

$$\frac{[\text{PbNO}_3^+]}{[\text{Pb}^{2+}] \times [\text{NO}_3^-]} = K \quad \dots \quad (18)$$

Assuming the whole of the complex to be either $\text{PbOH}\cdot\text{NO}_3$ or PbNO_3^+ , the constants K_1 and K are calculated. The values are shown in Table IIb and IIc. Neither K nor K_1 are strictly constant. The former increases and the latter decreases with decreasing concentration of hydrogen ion. Besides, K is very nearly constant at the higher hydrogen ion concentration and changes rapidly towards lower acid concentration range. The variation of K_1 is just opposite to that of K , and is very nearly constant values are found at the lower acid concentration range. The value of K_1 in lower acid range in Table IIc is very nearly 5 and agrees with the value obtained in the neutral solution (Table IIa) at about ionic strength of 0.3. The value of K_1 in pure nitric acid series (Table IIb) in the lower acid range (ionic strength, 0.02) is very nearly the same as that obtained in the neutral solution at about the same ionic strength.

These results indicate the existence of both the complexes PbNO_3^+ and $\text{PbOH}\cdot\text{NO}_3$ in nitric acid or mixture of nitric acid and sodium nitrate solution. The complex in neutral solution is most probably $\text{PbOH}\cdot\text{NO}_3$.

Using the values of K_1 , obtained with sodium nitrate solution at a particular ionic strength, and the value of $[\text{PbOH}^+]$ and $[\text{NO}_3^-]$ in nitric acid or mixture of sodium nitrate and nitric acid of the same ionic strength, the values of $[\text{PbOH}\cdot\text{NO}_3]$ were calculated. The concentration of PbNO_3^+ was obtained by subtracting $[\text{PbOH}\cdot\text{NO}_3]$ from $[\text{complex}]$. The values of K_1 were recalculated, and shown in Tables IIIa and IIIb respectively for pure nitric acid and mixture of sodium nitrate and nitric acid series. The results, though not very good, may be taken as constant. The equilibrium constants of the reaction

given by equation (20) is also calculated.

$$\frac{[\text{PbOH}\cdot\text{NO}_3] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{PbNO}_3^+]} = K_2 \quad \dots \quad (20)$$

The calculated values are shown in Tables IIIa and IIIb. The hydrolysis constant k_1 is also calculated by equation (5). The mean values of K , K_1 , K_2 and k_1 at ionic strength 0.3 are 3.83, 4.94, 0.186 and 0.161 respectively. It is interesting to note that K and K_1 are very nearly equal, and K_2 and k_1 are also very nearly equal. The value of k_1 obtained agrees with those reported in the previous paper by the authors.